

Role of Community Engagement in Technology Innovation System (TIS): A case of an Off-grid solar PV electrification system at Umerkot, Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract

Provision of electricity can bring betterment to any human's life by augmenting up the levels of health, education, social status, prosperity, and technology. However, access to grid electricity is limited due to inappropriate terrain for grid installation and low socio-economic conditions unable to pay for expenses that occurred and services taken. Thus the provision of electricity through grid seems to be an expensive option. When the possibility of grid electricity is slim, the many chances for off-grid energy systems are promoted by many stakeholders. It serves as curative support to rural areas that are already poverty-ridden. Among many off-grid technologies existing, the solar photovoltaic (PV) is advocated for its high potential to generate electricity efficiently with lower means of expenses.

Nonetheless, any rural off-grid solar systems' sustainability often uncovers problems far from financial and operational nature. The mere disposal of such an approach to a rural community requires some mechanism to promote collectiveness and effectiveness, leveraging the community engagement model to foster the system's proper operations and maintenance, impacting its sustainability. The process for any technology from its initiation and adoption to its diffusion is a whole process in itself. It results in new social and economic settings only possible by actors and stakeholders' activities influencing the system. This next-level process from technology diffusion to an institutionalized system is mainly called the technological innovation system (TIS). Studies on TIS have been conducted to discourse the process and challenges of development and diffusion of renewable energy technologies, mainly in developed countries.

Nevertheless, very few works have been put on TIS's significance and the role of its system functions on developing and emerging economies. Based on the

longitudinal methodology, this paper attempts to review and analyze best practices and challenges within community engagement and its role in a buildup of system functions inclined to the diffusion of PV technology by establishing TIS around this field in Pakistan. Our case study highlights the broader application of the TIS framework in the context for which it was born. The study recommends a policy involvement in structuring healthy TIS for quicker diffusion and further developing solar PV-based systems in Pakistan.

Keywords: *Technology Innovation System (TIS); Community Engagement; Off-grid solar PV electrification.*

Introduction and Context:

Providing access to affordable and sustainable electricity to rural and marginalized populations of any developing country poses many challenges and complications. The betterment of entrance to modern energy means and relevant services for developing countries, which accounts for over two and half billion, has been a critical aspect of globally sustainable development efforts [1]. The justifying reason to this claim can be validated by observing among 17 SDG's by United Nations, the two, i.e., sustainable energy (SDG 7) and combating climate change (SDG13), are directed towards transforming scenario of lack of access to electricity, yet by providing ends through which almost all other SDG's are contributed. Undoubtedly the lack of provision to electricity influences decreasing poverty trends, deteriorating life quality, motivated migration from rural areas to towns for better employment, and imbalance of sustainable socio-economic conditions that otherwise would significantly be reduced by bringing accessible and clean electricity. [2]

Nevertheless, increasing the living situations for people in rural areas, providing electricity is

mandatory. Countries like Singapore and Thailand have already met the target of 100% access to electricity for their residential regions [3]. As per a recent report published by International Energy Agency (IEA), over 1.35 billion people worldwide have no provision and access to electricity; however, developing countries such as Uganda and Bangladesh are still struggling with achieving nationwide electricity. In emerging economies such as Pakistan itself, where 61% population is based in rural areas [4] and is on rapid development with 97.53% (population's access to grid-electricity) already, still, there are many small hamlets and villages in rural areas that lack access to even grid electricity [5].

However, access to grid electricity is prohibited. It thus poses challenges such as high expense, inappropriate terrain for grid installation, and low socio-economic conditions to not pay for expenses that occurred and services taken. The possibility of grid electricity is slim. Many stakeholders promote the many chances for off-grid energy systems as it serves remedial support to rural areas that are already poverty-ridden. Among many off-grid technologies existing, the solar photovoltaic (PV) is advocated due to its high potential to generate electricity-efficient yet lower means of expenses [6].

Nonetheless, the sustainability of any rural off-grid solar systems often uncovers problems far from financial and operational. The mere disposal of such an approach to a rural community requires some mechanism within the community that could engage in a way to promote collectiveness and skills that makes a community engagement model not just foster proper operations and maintenance of the system but also help sustain it. It is estimated for any rural electrification programs to be successfully effective, it necessitates technical and managerial skills to develop a community engagement [5]. Thus, the systems have to devise strategies and policies to go through a prior negotiation and training to form a hierarchical process. Each stage has different people performing various roles equipped with specific training and resources to supervise the activity and its sustainability. Additionally, this community engagement brings in the amalgamation and institutionalization that help build effective service and robust people changes and other involvements.

However, it first has to achieve a lower level of market diffusion for any technology to achieve this community engagement. In contrast, a systematic approach is processed to understand this amalgamation of various factors, being community engagement to institutionalize how technology is promoted, diffused, and implemented. The recognized understanding of innovation and diffusion for any technology recommends that the overview and implementation of new technology are significant for both group and individual efforts [7]. In a simple sense, the whole process for any technology from its initiation, adoption to diffusion is a fundamental process in itself into new social and economic settings that are the activities' results by actors and people influenced by the system and exploiting the system. This next-level process from technology diffusion to an institutionalized system is mainly called the technological innovation system (TIS) [8]. It is believed that a TIS is to influence the proportion and scope of diffusion of newly introduced technology into society. In the much broader sense, it can be claimed that a TIS inspires the absorption of new technology by actors and community at all in full filling its required activities to sustain its existence and deal with pressing challenges such as high cost, lower level of awareness, and lack of legitimacy [9]. Nevertheless, there are various barriers to technology diffusion, and the transformation from traditional energy sources to renewable energy has been much intimately perplexing, especially in developing countries [10]. The primary problem is that these technologies diffuse into a real community that has their economic and social issues, impacting its successful implementation [11]. A right adoption for any off-grid requires the active involvement of a community so that the whole process of technology diffusion stimulates the development of a technological innovation system (TIS) [12].

A. Research Question

The study is conducted to research the following question:

What role do the community engagement and relevant practices contribute to the successful implementation of a technology innovation system for the off-grid rural electrification system?

B. Research Objectives

- To identify best practices of community engagement for successful technology diffusion to develop a technology innovation system.
- Investigate current status in solar PV based rural off-grid electrification technology innovation system building in Sindh, Pakistan.
- To explore the bottlenecks and hurdles of technology diffusion for effective development of technology innovation system.
- To propose recommendations for future actions and policy work.

Literature Review:

Factually, Pakistan has always been an energy importer, which creates a massive responsibility on the government and energy department's side to become dependent on many international forces. Meanwhile, it limited itself mainly on fossil fuels, but the oil-importing cost was also a burden on Pakistan's foreign exchange reserves with its rising prices. The overall energy demand was creating additional pressure to find a sustainable solution. Therefore to meet this demand, the Government of Pakistan, in its new budget for 2014-2015, allocated around \$340 million to its energy development activities and initiatives. A sizable portion of the budget will be expensed on generating power from solar and biogas [13].

Rural electrification is a way-out to provide electricity to those repressed population that are not grid-connected. However, it is surrounded by multiple challenges. Conventionally, electricity has been generated and disseminated by centralized private or public sector energy utility companies with somehow natural monopolies. However, in countries that are still underdeveloped, the electric utilities and regulators often either fail or struggle with specific resources and material availability to carry out the rural electrification system. In recent times, the deficiencies of traditional rural electrification projects have formed a demand for alternative solutions.

The leading is off-grid electrification, in which electricity is generated without any connection to the national electricity grid. A very nominal off-grid project can deploy solar panels and generate electricity for households' domestic and local needs in a tiny community. The off-grid approach of generating electricity comes with various advantages: lack of dependence on the national electricity grid,

restricted capital requirements, and easy access to remote rural communities.

The decentralized grid-based electrification system has become the most common approach and method for renewable energy technology, particularly solar PV (photovoltaic) systems. The selection of PV technology covers many, as of its high potential, low cost, but it is also suitable for areas where it is technoeconomically not feasible to expand the electricity via the national grid. In contrast, Pakistan has a high solar potential irradiation across its countryside to be estimated at around 4.5-7.0 kWh/m²/day. Also, as per some IEA estimations, solar energy's potential can help generate over 11 % of global energy demands in 2050 [14].

The speedy disposition of solar photovoltaic (PV), led by China and India, stimulates the emergence of solar, becoming the most significant source of low-carbon capacity by 2040, for which the estimated share of renewables in total power generation will reach 40% [13].

Study of Innovation Systems (IS) and particularly technological innovation system (TIS)

The study of innovation systems (IS) has caught much attention from notable researchers and policymakers since its introduction in 1980 [15], [16], [17]. Besides, everyone IS are not the same, and thus it differentiates and is analyzed on technological, sectoral, and national levels in which the focus revolves around its technology, industry, and geography [16], [17], [18]. However, what remains the same is every IS's objective, i.e., to develop, diffuse and consume new technology and the knowledge imparted from its technological leverages [19], [20].

In technological innovation system (TIS) literature, it is mainly concerned with understanding the reasons for technical innovation in the emergence of new innovative systems such as biogas, solar photovoltaic technologies, electric vehicles, etc. Thus, the critical elements of any TIS are its 'system functions.' The research by some TIS authors has identified and validated seven such functions, i.e. (1) entrepreneurial activities, (2) knowledge development, (3) knowledge diffusion, (4) guidance of the search, (5) market formation, (6) mobilization of resources, and (7)

creation of legitimacy [21]. However, the studies have also signified the interaction of actors, preferably the community beneficiaries, to collaborate. Moreover, along with functions, the literature also decides between 'structural dimensions,' which refers to networks and associations between agents and their infrastructure [22].

In one study, it is defined technological information systems TIS as "a vibrant network of representatives who involve interacting in a particular community within a specifically organized infrastructure or set of infrastructures to work collaboratively to generate, diffuse and utilize the technology" [17]. Another study also highlighted TIS as a set of network(s) of actors and communities that collaboratively interrelate and cooperate to contribute to the successful implantation, diffusion, and development of a technological innovation system (TIS) [23]. One of the system functions that is hugely involved in TIS's success is community involvement by structural interaction among the actors that serve as beneficiaries and network agents [19].

Methodology

Process way-out and design adaptations:

The main objective revolves around observing the activities and processes related to the community who are, in fact, beneficiaries of this project, furthermore their collaborations and structure. To achieve this, a longitudinal methodology has been employed [24]. This method is frequently used to analyze anyone or more functional parameters that influence TIS. For an overview, see the work of [25].

The longitudinal methodology includes quantitative analysis, where the data shall be gathered employing two

Stages. Primary data has been collected through a survey from community people to observe their perceptions and beliefs. In the second stage, the primary data has been collected from stakeholders/actors to see their longitudinal performance over time within community engagement perspective TIS development.

A. Sample

The sample and audience that we surveyed belong to Village Revi Ji Dhani, located in Union Council Faqir Abdullah at a distance of approximately 25 kilometers in south of Umerkot City province of Sindh Pakistan. The village with a population of 187 is the direct beneficiaries of the Solar Powered PV system by IEEE SIGHT Karachi.

Among 187 residents, 37 are female, and 35 are male, while the rest are children's depending on parents. Moreover, the number of boys older than five years is 55, while the number of girls older than five years is 25, the rest 35 are kids below the age of 5 years old. The only vocation that men were involved in was carpeting, and wall painter and women and households work on a part-time basis to stitch cultural clothes and shirts.

B. Data Collection

At both stages, the community engagement survey, initial and post-project, contained ten (10) multiple-choice questions (Likert Scale of 5 for each question), which took on average four to five minutes to complete. The survey form questions circled areas: a) Life experiences without electricity, b) Awareness about electricity and its access c) need and demand for the proper electricity system, d) Chances of acceptability for a rural off-grid system.

One of the essential issues with the data collection was to brief that we are not advocating/attacking any governmental or NGO policy or program. Instead, we seek to determine public opinion, so the defendants were more honest and open with responses—the collection and wording of questions inclined the type of responses received and bias in answers. The survey form was constructed as necessary to help understand the demands and purchasing power for an off-grid

electrification system. The initial survey consisted of one full day field visit to the location followed by a post-project survey conducted after three months to see possible effects and changes in the resident's lives after having rural electrification off-grid installed.

The study also benefitted from focus group sessions after survey completion, where some (average 8-10 people) participated voluntarily for a 30-40 minute discussion outside their houses.

Results and Findings

A. Discussion

The project was technical, but due to understanding the role of community involvement in sustaining its existence, an emphasis was also put to develop and maintain one of its own kinds' Operational and Maintenance Committee O&M. The O&M committee consisted of people such as local NGO representative, IEEE SIGHT Karachi representative, an elder from the community, a youth capable enough to read and write basic and a women leader to form a community-based team to manage the operations and successful run for the project. Moreover, the capacity building to augment up the local communities' ability to run a PV system to raise awareness among users to guarantee the chances of acceptability by the community. Furthermore, to safeguard the need for proper maintenance by each household, an MoU was also signed by IEEE SIGHT Karachi, and residents drafted in the local Sindhi language to assess the contract better. This innovative community involvement group hunted to address the socio-economic particulars of the secluded and rural populations to satisfactorily reinforce the local capacity in order to pledge the long-term sustainability of the services.

There were also some cautionary procedures shared with the community that the system needs no consideration other than intermittent careful cleaning of the plates to eradicate dirt. For the proper documentation, Reve Ji Dhani village group took advantage of publishing the receipt book and stamp & starting to collect the monthly household charges at the end of September 2017. Each month, this was to be collected a household usage fees to maintain a treasury account opened on a joint-sharing basis.

B. Practical Implications

Some implications that occurred during the tenure of the project are as follows;

- **Social Acceptance of project** – Due to a lack of awareness and education, many villagers were skeptical about solar PV systems based on their stereotyped religious and faithful beliefs. They resisted by themselves and tried to exploit others into believing it is a trap to undo their religious trusts.
- **Operation and Maintenance responsibility-** There involved much discussion both individually and in the group to understand what community involvement model is required and will be suitable to maintain its sustainability.
- **Pressure and threats from local government officers-** Considering such projects and incentives to gauge the interest of villagers to vote for their political parties and leaders, a few government electives and officers felt the project team that was entirely non-partisan and not for profit to belong to any other political party and cause and thus a small resistance and pressure to close down the project was also experienced.

C. Policy Suggestions

The following policy suggestions are deemed for researchers on off-grid TIS networks, NGO workers interested in the field, and in-fact municipal governments to create local community-based groups to create more sustainable solutions.

- **One model does not suit all conditions-** Initially, the project team decided to install a central rural off-grid electrification PV system for the whole community and then provide a separate DC energy source for each household as per its need; however, the differences across unity of this community, it was later decided to install a separate PV system for each household and instead invest on creating a village-based group to maintain its O&M facilities.
- **A strong governance arrangement is a must** – There have been many rural-based off-grid projects in the same community and district by other NGOs and student groups, yet what made them fail was not an appropriate strong governance structure involving the community whole to make a deciding body.
- **Capacity development is urgent to sustain -** The project can go successful until every end is

intact. However, when any troubleshooting or immediate action is required, it is the local villagers. These actual beneficiaries can repair or fix it only if they are capable of doing it; making it sustainable an emphasis on capacity development is urgent.

- **Introduce linkages of the project with the rural improvement activities** – Doing such creates an interaction between what traditionally villagers used to do and what they could be doing now with the access of electricity such as employment options or help. This can also improve the money-flow into the community to pay usage fees on time and contribute more.
- **Develop an eco-system of off-grid rural electrification systems** – To safeguard the sustainability of off-grid electrification system at any village for the long-term, an entire supply chain has to developed to leverage from each other learnings and experiences. If locally manufactured and assembled the whole off-grid system components, it can create an employment opportunity in parallel for villagers and help train a pool of skillful operators.

Conclusion

Provision to electricity can bring betterment to any human's life by augmenting up the levels of health, education, social status, prosperity, and technology. In poverty as a multidimensional problem, among various known indicators such as physical weakness, low hygiene, lack of access to education, and lower income earnings, the energy consumption and availability are also an indicator now to distinguish poor from the one that is not poor. A recent study has analyzed and defined that within the essential quality of life, social values, and community needs, the annual electricity consumption of 1000 kW h per year per capita is known as the margin between basic life situations and assured survival [26].

Also, to highlight the significance, the studies conducted [17] and [21] to understand the development, diffusion, and utilization of new energy technology is significantly subjective to be impacted by the establishment of technological innovation system (TIS) centering the technology as its core focus. The existence of well-functioning TIS is understood to foster the diffusion of technologies via

satisfaction of its relevant vital activities and processes known as system functions. Moreover, the TIS studies on renewable energy technologies were steered primarily in developed countries (for example, the Dutch photovoltaic innovation system [27].

References

- i. T. Takama, F. Lambe, F. Johnson, A. Arvidson, B. Atanassov, M. Debebe, L. Nilsson, P. Tella, S. Tsephel, *Will African consumers buy cleaner fuels and stoves? A household energy economic analysis model for the market introduction of bio-ethanol cooking stoves in Ethiopia, Tanzania and Mozambique, research report, Stockholm Environmental Institute, 2011*
- ii. Cherni J and Preston F. *Rural Electrification under liberal reforms; the case of Peru, Journal of Cleaner Production, 2007; 15,143-52).*
- iii. Urmee T, Harries D, Schlapfer A. *Issues related to rural electrification using renewable energy in developing countries of Asia and Pacific. Renewable Energy 2009; 34:354–7.*
- iv. *Pakistan Energy Situation- Energypedia. Published in 2016, accessible at: https://energypedia.info/wiki/Pakistan_Energy_Situation [accessed on 20th February, 2018]*
- v. *World Bank. Data Bank, 2017. Available at <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator>*
- vi. Dornan, M., 2011. *Solar-based rural electrification policy design: the renewable energy service company (RESCO) model in Fiji. Renew. Energy 36 (2), 797–803.*
- vii. C. Edquist, B. Johnson, *Institutions and organizations in systems of innovation, in: C. Edquist (Ed.), Systems of Innovation—Technologies, Institutions and Organizations Institutions and Organizations in Systems of Innovation, Pinter, London, 1997.*
- viii. Negro, M.P. Hekkert, R.E. Smits, *Explaining the failure of the Dutch innovation system for biomass digestion—a functional analysis, Energy Policy 35 (2) (2007) 925–938.*

- ix. A. Bergek, S. Jacobsson, B. Carlsson, S. Lindmark, A. Rickne, *Analyzing the functional dynamics of technological innovation systems: a scheme of analysis*, *Res. Policy* 37 (3) (2008) 407–429.
- x. Mondal, M.A.H., Kamp, L.M., Pachova, N., 2010. Drivers, barriers, and strategies for implementation of renewable energy technologies in rural areas in Bangladesh-an innovation system analysis. *Energ Policy* 38, 4626–4634.
- xi. Rogers, E.M., 2003. *Diffusion of Innovations*. 5th ed. Free Press, New York
- xii. Antonelli, C., 2006. Localized technological change and factor markets: constraints and inducements to innovation. *Struct. Chang. Econ. Dyn.* 17, 224–247.
- xiii. International Energy Agency, 'WEO - Energy Access Database', 2016, <http://www.worldenergyoutlook.org/resources/energydevelopment/energyaccessdatabase/>
- xiv. Zhang X, Zhao X, Smith S, Xu J, Yu X. Review of P&D Progress and practical application of the solar photovoltaic/thermal (PV/T) technologies. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2012; 16(1): 599-617
- xv. Freeman, C., 1987. *Technology Policy and Economic Performance: Lessons from Japan*. Printer Publishers, London
- xvi. Lundvall, B.-A., 1992. *National Systems of Innovation: Towards a Theory of Innovation and Interactive Learning*. Pinter Publishers, London.
- xvii. Carlsson, B., Stankiewicz, R., 1991. On the nature, function, and composition of technological systems. *Evol. Econ.* 1, 93–118.
- xviii. Malerba, F., 2002. Sectoral systems of innovation and production. *Res. Policy* 31 (2), 247–264
- xix. Jacobsson, S., Johnson, A., 2000. The diffusion of renewable energy technology: an analytical framework and key issues for research. *Energ Policy* 28 (9), 625–640.
- xx. Edquist, C., 2005. *Systems of innovation: perspectives and challenges*. In: Fagerberg, J., Mowery, D.C., Nelson, R.R. (Eds.), *the Oxford Handbook of Innovation*. Oxford University Press, New York, pp. 181–208.
- xxi. Hekkert, M., Suurs, R.A.A., Negro, S., Kuhlmann, S., Smits, R., 2007. Functions of innovation systems: a new approach for analyzing technological change. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.* 74 (4), 413–432.
- xxii. Wieczorek, A.J., Hekkert, M.P., 2012. Systemic instruments for systemic innovation problems: a framework for policy makers and innovation scholars. *Sci. Public Policy* 39, 74–87.
- xxiii. Markard, J., Truffer, B., 2008. Technological innovation systems and the multi-level perspective: towards an integrated framework. *Res. Policy* 37, 596–615.
- xxiv. Aschalew D. Tigabu a, Frans Berkhout, Pieter van Beukering, 2013. Technology innovation systems and technology diffusion: Adoption of bio-digestion in an emerging innovation system in Rwanda
- xxv. A.H. Van de Ven, G.P. Huber, Longitudinal field research methods for studying processes of organizational change, *Organ. Sci.* 1 (1991) 213–219.
- xxvi. Pereira MG, Freitas MAV, da Silva NF. Rural electrification and energy poverty: empirical evidences from Brazil. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2010; 14:1229–40.
- xxvii. Negro, S.O., Vasseur, V., Van Sark, W.G.J.H.M., Hekkert, M.P., 2009. Understanding innovation system builds up: The rise and fall of the Dutch PV Innovation System. *Innovation Studies Utrecht (ISU) Working Paper Series 09*, pp. 1–34.